

ACCRUE index for the uncertainty reduction of effective multiplication factor in an LFR

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ABSTRACT

Predictive simulations for the design and safety assessment of advanced nuclear systems, such as the Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR), are limited by uncertainties in the underlying nuclear data (ND). Data assimilation is a possible route to reduce these ND uncertainties by combining prior information from nuclear data libraries with integral experiments, but which experiments are selected affect the posterior. This paper proposes and compares a data assimilation methodology that iteratively selects experiments from a set of filtered experiments using the ACCRUE-similarity-index. The method is compared against a selection based on a priori similarity coefficients (c_k -index). The analysis was performed on the ALFRED LFR model using 204 ICSBEP benchmarks and the JEFF-4.0 library. Results demonstrate that experiments selected iteratively via the ACCRUE-index yield a more efficient path to reduce the k_{eff} uncertainty in an LFR in comparison to selecting experiments based on a priori c_k values. This work analyses a posterior-informed, iterative selection strategy applied to an LFR and provides insights into the six most important nuclides contributing to the k_{eff} nuclear data uncertainties.

Keywords: Assimilation, criticality, sensitivity, ACCRUE, LFR

1. INTRODUCTION

The Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) is a promising advanced reactor concept included in the proposed Generation IV designs [1]. The development of LFRs, such as the LFR Small Modular Reactor (SMR) which SCK CEN is developing, presents unique challenges. As a first-of-a-kind (FOAK) system using liquid lead coolant and Mixed Oxide (MOX) fuel, its design and safety studies cannot be validated using existing experimental data that fully replicates its operational conditions. Consequently, the design of this reactor must rely heavily on predictive computational simulations.

As a first obstacle, the reliability of these simulations is significantly affected by uncertainty associated with nuclear data (ND). For LFRs, ND uncertainties are the dominant source of uncertainty in key reactor parameters, most notably the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) [2]. This high uncertainty inflates design margins, complicates safety assessments, and increases overall project costs. While targeted experiments could reduce these uncertainties, they are expensive and scarce, creating a need for methodologies that can efficiently leverage existing experimental data.

This paper proposes a systematic approach to reduce k_{eff} uncertainty in, but not limited to, LFR simulations by combining prior ND knowledge with selected high-quality integral criticality measurements via data assimilation. We argue that methods for selecting experiments, based on a predefined similarity-coefficient threshold like the c_k -similarity coefficient [3], result in useful information being not considered for an LFR, for which high c_k experiments are scarce. Instead, we employ an iterative approach that targets the largest source of common uncertainty remaining after each assimilation step.

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This allows experiments previously deemed irrelevant to become valuable as more dominant uncertainties are reduced.

We test the performance of the ACCRUE coefficient [4] that, unlike the c_k -similarity coefficient, also accounts for the accumulated effect of uncertainty reductions and experimental measurement uncertainties. In this sense, the best combination of experiments to minimize the target LFR's uncertainty is determined. The objective is to analyse methods to improve confidence in predictive simulations with regards to LFR design and safety assessment. This is done by assessing the impact on k_{eff} uncertainties and bias adjustment, while also highlighting the most important contributors to the k_{eff} uncertainty.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Theory

The prediction of neutronic properties of a nuclear systems relies on a neutron transport solver, geometry, material properties, code tailored settings and ND, each of which are subjected to some kind of uncertainty. It is important to evaluate the effect of these uncertainties in the context of design and safety studies for nuclear systems. While evaluating the full effect of the input variability by propagating the complete Probability Density Function (PDF) is impractical, estimating uncertainties using first-order approximations is viable. Here, the first-order derivative at the nominal value can be calculated using adjoint methods. The ND is the only parameter that is being reduced, since it is deemed as the largest contributor for effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) and is shared among simulations. Using the stochastic neutron transport solver, SERPENT-2 [5], an energy-dependent vector is computed describing the relative first-order derivatives of k_{eff} with respect to ND in the multi-group format ECCO-33 as

$$S_{R,\alpha} = \frac{\partial R/R}{\partial \alpha_n/\alpha_n} \quad , \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, M, \quad (1)$$

where $S_{R,\alpha}$ describes the relative change in a response R due to a relative change in α_n with n being the n^{th} energy group out of M energy groups, with the first-order derivative evaluated at the nominal point α_n . Generally, R and α can be respectively any response and input variable, but we only consider the response k_{eff} and variability in the ND. More specifically, we consider the most relevant reactions: elastic scattering (n,n), inelastic scattering (n,n'), fission (n,f), capture (n, γ), prompt neutron fission energy spectrum (χ_p) and prompt fission neutron multiplicity (ν_p).

These sensitivity coefficients can now be combined with the relative covariance matrix describing the variability in ND to calculate the variability in k_{eff} . Here, it is assumed that the ND PDF follows a Gaussian distribution and k_{eff} depends linearly on ND around its nominal value. The formula used to propagate the ND variability is often called the sandwich-formula [6] and is defined as

$$\text{Var}(R) = E[(R - \bar{R})^2] = S_{R,\alpha}^T \cdot \Sigma_\alpha \cdot S_{R,\alpha}, \quad (2)$$

where Σ_α represents the relative covariance matrix describing the ND variability in multi-group format, and $\text{Var}(R)$ is the relative variance of response R , here k_{eff} . Multiple systems can be combined by appending the sensitivity vectors in a sensitivity matrix. The solution will then be a covariance matrix with the variances on the diagonal and correlations between systems hidden in the off-diagonal terms. These correlation-terms, also called the Pearson-correlation coefficient or the c_k -similarity coefficient [3], describe how much of the k_{eff} uncertainty stems from ND uncertainties that are shared between the two systems. The similarity coefficient $c_k(1,2)$ between a system 1 and 2 can be calculated as

$$c_k(1,2) = \frac{\text{Cov}(1,2)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(1) \cdot \text{Var}(2)}} = \frac{S_1^T \Sigma_\alpha S_2}{\sqrt{S_1^T \Sigma_\alpha S_1} \cdot \sqrt{S_2^T \Sigma_\alpha S_2}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\text{Cov}(1,2)$ may be computed using Eq. 2 and $\text{Var}(1)$ and $\text{Var}(2)$ are the variances on the diagonal of Eq. 2. For the sake of simplicity, the subscript in $S_{R,\alpha}$ is replaced with a number representing the systems under consideration. The c_k similarity coefficient may be used to quantify the relevance of an experiment to an application as it explains how much ND uncertainties are in common. If the system is sufficiently relevant, possibly quantified using a threshold value, it can be selected to help improve predictive simulations of a target system using the Generalized Linear Least Squares (GLLS) formulas [6]. Here, a posterior ND vector α' is computed that minimizes the discrepancies between calculated c and measured m reactor responses and is constrained by the variability in ND setup by evaluators Σ_α . This minimization formula is described by

$$\chi^2 = [\alpha' - \alpha]^T \Sigma_\alpha^{-1} [\alpha' - \alpha] + [m - c]^T \Sigma_{\text{exp}}^{-1} [m - c], \quad (4)$$

where χ^2 is the parameter to be minimized, Σ_α is the prior covariance matrix of the ND and Σ_{exp} is the covariance matrix describing the experimental measurements. It should be noted that the correlations between experiments are not taken into account due to the difficulty of quantifying them. Additionally, one term is missing in this equation, being the term which describes the correlations between ND and experiments, which is also neglected. The resulting posterior ND vector α' and its covariance structure V'_α can be computed using

$$\frac{\alpha' - \alpha}{\alpha} = \Sigma_\alpha S (S^T \Sigma_\alpha S + \Sigma_{\text{exp}})^{-1} \frac{(m - c)}{c}, \quad (5)$$

$$\Sigma'_\alpha = \Sigma_\alpha - \Sigma_\alpha S (S^T \Sigma_\alpha S + \Sigma_{\text{exp}})^{-1} S^T \Sigma_\alpha^T, \quad (6)$$

here the prior ND vector α is updated with a term weighting the measurement and calculated discrepancy on the experimental and ND covariances, and transposing the result to the ND space. Similarly, the prior covariance matrix is updated. With the updated ND vector, the response of another system can be predicted using the sensitivity coefficients linking the ND with the k_{eff} of a given system using $R' = R_0 + S_{R,\alpha}^T \frac{\Delta\alpha}{\alpha} \cdot R_0$ where $\frac{\Delta\alpha}{\alpha}$ represents the relative difference between the posterior and prior ND vector. The posterior uncertainty on response R due to ND can be retrieved by inserting the posterior ND covariance Σ'_α in Eq. 2 and taking the square root of the diagonal.

When a posterior ND vector is obtained, its performance can be tested on a set of experiments which have not been included in the assimilation process using the χ^2 -metric. It quantifies the performance in terms of absolute discrepancy between the calculated and measured response relative to its experimental variance as

$$\chi_{\text{exp}}^2 = \frac{(k_{\text{exp}} - k_{\text{calc}})^2}{\Sigma_{\text{exp}}} = \frac{(k_{\text{exp}} - R')^2}{\Sigma_{\text{exp}}}, \quad (7)$$

in which only the experimental uncertainty is taken into account and the posterior χ_{exp}^2 is calculated using R' . It is also possible to include the ND uncertainty, however, since the ND uncertainty gets reduced significantly, the posterior χ_{exp}^2 might give a worse solution in comparison to the prior, therefore it is not calculated with ND uncertainties. In this work, experiments with an individual $\chi_{\text{exp}}^2 > 5$ are considered more likely to be biased, therefore they are filtered out.

2.2. ACCRUE

Up to now, we have shortly discussed how experiments may be selected to include in the assimilation process, i.e. calculating the c_k similarity coefficient and setting a threshold. And while this might be sufficient if enough similar experiments are available, other coefficients might be more useful when no high c_k experiments are available. One of such coefficients is the ACCRUE coefficient (short for Accumulative Correlation Coefficient for Relevance of Uncertainties in Experimental validation)[4].

Suppose we have a set of experiments $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}$ and a target application $A = \{a\}$. Then let B' be the smallest set of experiments that will reduce the uncertainty of target application A to a given threshold τ . To arrive to this set, the ACCRUE index (j_k) can be used to select which experiment should be selected that reduces the uncertainty the most given other experiments have already been included in the assimilation.

To start, the prior ND vector and covariance matrix are used to calculate the $j_k(b_i, a)$ -index between experiment b_i and application a as

$$j_k(b_i, a) = \frac{S_i^T \Sigma_\alpha S_a}{\sqrt{S_i^T \Sigma_\alpha S_i + \sigma_i^2} \cdot \sqrt{S_a^T \Sigma_\alpha S_a}}. \quad (8)$$

In this equation, the experimental uncertainty of experiment b_i is included in σ_i^2 . Then for all experiments in the set B , calculate the j_k -index and select the most relevant experiment using $m_1 = \arg \max_{b_i \in B} \{j_k(b_i, a)\}$. Then experiment m_1 will be added to the set of selected experiments $M = \{m_1\}$, which is used to calculate a posterior ND vector and covariance matrix using Eq. 5 and Eq. 6. Using the posterior ND vector and its covariance matrix, the j_k index can then again be calculated for the set $B' = B \setminus M$. The sensitivity coefficients are assumed to be constant and are therefore not recalculated at each step. This process iteratively continues until a certain k_{eff} uncertainty threshold τ is reached or the maximum number of elements in the set M is reached. The c_k -index calculates the experiment which shares the largest source of uncertainty with another system. In contrast, the j_k index calculates the experiment which can reduce the uncertainty of an application the most, as it accounts for accumulated uncertainty reductions and the experimental uncertainty.

2.3. Models

The aim of this paper is to compare how different criteria for selecting experiments affect the posterior application response, with the focus on an LFR. By doing so, the posterior response uncertainty due to ND can be dissected to highlight the most important contributors. The model for the LFR is taken to be the Advanced Lead-cooled Fast Reactor European Demonstrator (ALFRED) [7]. It is a fast spectrum reactor cooled with liquid lead using MOX fuel in the inner core enriched to 20.5 wt% and the outer core enriched to 26.2 wt%.

A set of 204 experiments is obtained from the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) handbook [8]. SERPENT-2 models for these were obtained through the OECD/NEA database of input models. In Table I, an overview of the categories of experiments can be seen. The abbreviations stand for Highly Enriched Uranium (HEU), Mixed (MIX), Plutonium (Pu), Metallic (MET), Fast spectrum (FAST) and Intermediate spectrum (INTER). For each of the models, a sensitivity vector was calculated using 1000 active cycles with each 20 000 particles and 15 latent generations.

2.4. Nuclear data

For all of the simulations, the JEFF-4.0 [9] ND library was used. The covariance matrices were generated in the ECCO-33 energy group structure starting from the JEFF-4.0 library using SANDY [10] which interacts with NJOY2016. For some reactions, the processed ND uncertainties were unreasonably large

Table I. Overview of number of experiments in each category available in B

Category	# experiments	# unfiltered experiments
HEU-MET-FAST	166	132
MIX-MET-FAST	6	6
PU-MET-FAST	29	26
PU-MET-INTER	3	2
Total	204	166

($\geq 1000\%$), this was the case for ^{16}O , ^{17}O , ^{36}Ar , ^{63}Cu , ^{113}Cd and ^{10}B . In these cases, the covariance matrix was taken from the JEFF-3.3 evaluated ND library. For nuclides which had no covariance information in JEFF-4.0 and JEFF-3.3, the covariance information was neglected, this was the case for ^{113}Cd and ^{14}N .

2.5. Data assimilation process

By combining the equations just described, a process is setup to carefully select experiments that most efficiently reduce the uncertainty of a certain application. A χ^2 filter is also included to try not to include models which contain model biases. A flowchart describing the process is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart describing the general methodology.

We start with a set of experiments B and at first a filter is applied to check if the χ_{exp}^2 is larger than a predefined threshold. If so, the probability of having bias in either the model or in the experiment is expected to be larger. Therefore, we would rather select an experiment that is less prone to bias, so we filter it out.

Subsequently, an experiment is selected based on a selection criterion. In this paper, three selection criteria are compared, the c_k -similarity coefficient evaluated using the prior ND covariances, the c_k index evaluated using posterior covariances and the ACCRUE j_k -index. In both cases, in each iteration, the experiment resulting in the largest selection index is selected. Additionally, after each iteration, the posterior performance (using Eq. 7) is evaluated on the set of remaining experiments.

Eventually, after 30 iterations (or when a certain posterior k_{eff} uncertainty is reached), the prior and posterior ND vectors and covariance matrices are used to compare the bias and uncertainties present in the application (i.e. the ALFRED model at Beginning of Life (BoL)).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first step, experiments are filtered based on Eq. 7. From the 204 ICSBEP criticality experiments, 38 experiments were filtered due to having a χ_{exp}^2 higher than 5. Some of which were previously identified

as inaccurate.

In Figure 2, the bias and uncertainty evolution for the ALFRED model is shown when experiments are selected from the filtered set using one of the two selection criteria (i.e. prior c_k and j_k) until 30 iterations have been performed. First benchmarks are selected based on the c_k -similarity coefficient calculated using the prior covariance matrices. Secondly, experiments are selected based on the j_k -similarity coefficient evaluated using the posterior ND covariances each time a new experiment is added to the assimilation, it also takes into account experimental uncertainties. Finally, the result of doing an assimilation using all non-filtered experiments available in the set of experiments is shown in black.

Figure 2. Comparison of the bias (lines) and associated response uncertainty due to ND (shaded area) computed with the posterior ND covariances. Final bias and uncertainty given in the legend in pcm.

A third method where we reevaluate the c_k -index in each iteration using the posterior ND covariances was also tested but it was found to yield the exact same result as using the j_k -index. When c_k^{prior} and j_k are compared, the bias is found to correspond well between the two predictions and does not differ significantly from including all non-filtered experiments, although the ND uncertainties reduce significantly faster when using j_k .

In the left plot of Figure 3, the prior c_k -index is compared for the experiments selected in each method. Here it is clear that experiments which are deemed irrelevant under prior assumptions can become more relevant conditionally that other experiments have already been included. For example, the third experiment selected in the j_k algorithm has a prior c_k value of around 0.3. Meaning that based on prior information it would not bring much additional information. But due to the uncertainties being reduced by experiments one and two, the third experiment becomes the most relevant out of the remaining experiments. Additionally, the 15th and 16th experiments have a c_k value of close to zero, still they get prioritized before the 17th experiment is selected which has a c_k value around 0.6. In the right plot of Figure 3, the χ_{exp}^2 is shown on the remaining experiments. Surprisingly, the method c_k^{prior} seems to perform remarkably worse in comparison to j_k .

When we now compare the uncertainty contribution of the prior and posterior ND, we can gain more insights into areas that were improved, mostly the fuel materials. In Figure 4, the six most important prior and j_k posterior k_{eff} uncertainty contributors are given. When a new experiment is designed, the posterior uncertainties can be targeted, hereby possibly targeting areas under-represented in the suite of experiments already available. It must be noted however, that the posterior uncertainties have been reduced to the minimum uncertainty given the experimental uncertainty. If this uncertainty is to be reduced more, more accurate or sensitive experiments are required. Additionally, it can be seen that uncertainties in ^{206}Pb are barely reduced, which indicates that the uncertainties due to other nuclides were more important, although they cannot be reduced much further.

Figure 3. Prior c_k value (left) and χ_{exp}^2 on the remaining experiments (right) evaluated in each iteration step.

Figure 4. Top 6 most contributing nuclides to the k_{eff} uncertainty in pcm.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Nuclear data (ND) uncertainties are a primary source of uncertainty in predictive simulations of advanced nuclear systems. We have studied this in particular for the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) of a Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR). While data assimilation can be used to reduce these uncertainties, its effectiveness depends on which integral experiments are included. This paper proposed and tested a data assimilation approach that iteratively selects experiments based on the ACCRUE-similarity-index from a set of filtered experiments. This approach was compared with selecting experiments based on a static, a priori and a posteriori c_k -index. The analysis was performed on the ALFRED LFR model using 204 ICSBEP benchmarks and the JEFF-4.0 library. We show that a selection of 30 experiments with high a priori similarity (high c_k) is slightly less efficient at reducing the target application's uncertainty than a set of 30 experiments iteratively selected using the ACCRUE-index. This is because the iterative method includes lower-similarity experiments that cover unique portions of the ND uncertainty not addressed by the high-similarity experiments. One of the limitations is the lower limit of the posterior uncertainties which is determined by the experimental uncertainty, therefore more accurate experiments or experiments with a higher sensitivity to specific nuclear data are needed to reduce uncertainties even

further. This work confirms that an iterative, posterior-informed selection strategy can be employed to increase the efficiency of data assimilation. Future work will apply this process to evaluate the potential impact of new or proposed experimental measurements.

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